

AtecA Room Observation Grid

Category	Aspect	Details	Data
Classroom Design	Furniture Layout	Note arrangement and types of furniture.	Las equipos observados: Impresoras 3D, Pantallas Verdes, Projectores LED, sillas y mobiliario para el
Classroom Design	Space Utilization	Evaluate effective use of space.	En la mayoría de los centros visitados, la distribución de los espacios es adecuada.
Classroom Design	Presence of Technology	Record types of tech equipment like digital boards, projectors, computers.	Pantallas digitales, ordenadores potentes (para audiovisuales y realidad aumentada), proyectores
Educational Resources	Available Educational Material	List all physical and digital materials.	Material digital: Text Documents, Word documents, PDFs, Text files
Educational Resources	Use of Multimedia Resources	Incorporation of multimedia tools in learning.	Utilizan las herramientas multimedia del aula AtecA para realizar pruebas y proyectos relacionados a la
Educational Resources	Adapted Resources	Identify tailored resources for diverse needs.	Cada aula AtecA esta mayormente adaptada a una familia profesional y en ella se pueden adaptar las
Classroom Interactions	Class Dynamics	Describe methods like debates, group work, presentations.	Desarrollan proyectos y los discuten en sesiones de prueba y evalúan aplicaciones y usos de lo
Classroom Interactions	Teacher-Student Relationship	Nature of interactions between teachers and students.	El maestro funciona como guía de la interacción, escoge líderes que tomen el control del desarrollo al estudiantado tener mayor protagonismo, son ellos
Classroom Interactions	Student Participation	Assess engagement with class activities.	los que dan pauta al dinamismo y desarrollo de las el docente o el mentor (encargado TIC) guía al
Technology and Learning	Integration of Technology	Document technology use in activities.	alumnado en el uso de las herramientas
Technology and Learning	Educational Platforms and Apps	Note specific platforms or applications used.	Mocap, Rokoko Studio Mixamo (Adobe) FBX reviewer, Blender
Technology and Learning	Internet Access and Usage	Record availability and use of internet.	Conexión a internet habilitada, autoconexión a Edurroom
Inclusion and Diversity	Curricular Adaptations	Adaptations for students with specific needs.	
Inclusion and Diversity	Inclusion Strategies	Strategies used to include all students.	Todos los estudiantes reunidos en un grupos para probar los productos y ver los proyectos para ayudar
Inclusion and Diversity	Support for Cultural and Linguistic Diversity	Support for cultural and linguistic diversity.	si bien los docentes desarrollan las actividades en Catalán los alumnos pueden responder en su lengua aunque no hay un metodo especifico para el uso
Evaluation and Feedback	Evaluation Methods	List and describe evaluation methods.	del Aula AtecA se observa el uso de estrategias
Evaluation and Feedback	Frequency and Type of Feedback	Note frequency and types of feedback.	retroalimentación inmediata
Evaluation and Feedback	Tools for Tracking Progress	Identify tools for monitoring progress.	asistencia del docente-alumno, alumno-alumno para aclarar duda sobre procesos. Preguntas recurrentes
Learning Environment and Climate	Emotional Environment	Observe the emotional tone and climate.	Los alumnos expresan que el Aula AtecA es el mejor espacio del instituto. se muestran contento de tener
Learning Environment and Climate	Engagement and Commitment	Assess participation and engagement.	
Learning Environment and Climate	Promotion of Respect and Collaboration	Practices promoting respect and collaboration.	
Teacher Training and Support	Teacher Training Programs	Information about training programs.	no existe un programa de entrenamiento en el uso del aula AtecA
Teacher Training and Support	Institutional Support	Support for innovative methodologies.	No hay una metodología transversal pasa el uso del aula AtecA
Teacher Training and Support	Teacher Competence in Educational Technology	Proficiency in educational technology.	No está establecido, pero el certificado de la CDD e se ha realizado en base a meritos adquiridos
Time Management	Class Time Distribution	How time is allocated during classes.	se manejan los tiempos en base a las horas reservadas
Time Management	Efficiency in Activity Development	Efficiency of activity execution.	las actividades se desarrollan de manera eficiente, salvo que la conectividad a internet falle
Time Management	Flexibility in Planning	Adaptability to changes.	
Student Perceptions	Student Opinions on Learning Environment	Gather students' views of their environment.	En general es positiva e motivadora...
Student Perceptions	Satisfaction with Methodologies and Resources	Assess satisfaction with methodologies and resources.	Aun no queda claro
Student Perceptions	Suggestions for Improvement	Collect improvement suggestions.	Necesita de capacitación en metodologías transversales para el uso del Aula AtecA